

DRIVER DROWSINESS DETECTION SYSTEM USING IMAGE PROCESSING

Mohammad Rizwan Sami¹, Yasareni Shravya²,
Banala Sindhuja³, Mrs. V. Somalaxmi⁴

^{1,2,3} UG Student, Dept. of ECE, CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

⁴ Assistant Professor, Dept. of ECE,
CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

ABSTRACT

The advancement in computer vision has assisted drivers in the form of automatic self-driving cars etc. The misadventure are caused by driver's fatigue and drowsiness about 20%. It poses a serious problem for which several approaches were proposed. However, they are not suitable for real-time processing. The major challenges faced by these methods are robustness to handle variation in human face and lightning conditions. We aim to implement an intelligent processing system that can reduce road accidents drastically. This approach enables us to identify driver's face characteristics like eye closure percentage, eye-mouth aspect ratios, blink rate, yawning, head movement, etc. In this system, the driver is continuously monitored by using a webcam. The driver's face and the eye are detected using haar cascade classifiers. Eye images are extracted and fed to Custom designed Convolutional Neural Network for classifying whether both left and

right eye are closed. Based on the classification, the eye closure score is calculated. If the driver is found to be drowsy, an alarm will be triggered

INTRODUCTION

Many safety connected driving supporter schemes decreased the danger of four-wheeler accidents, and investigations depicted weariness to be a major reason of four-wheeler accidents. A car organization announced an idea that whole deadly accidents (17%) would be attributed to weary drivers. Many revisions showed by Volkswagen AG specify that 5-25% of all accidents are produced by the sleeping of driver. The lack of concentration damage steering actions and decrease response period, and revisions illustrated that sleepiness raises threat of crashes demand for a dependable intelligent driver sleepiness sensing system. The aim is to create an intelligent processing scheme to avoid road accidents. This can be done by period of time monitoring the drowsiness and

warning driver of inattention to prevent accidents. Based on the literature survey, the driver's drowsiness can be detected based on three factors such as physiological, behavioral, and vehicle-based measurements. But these approaches pose some disadvantages in certain real-time scenarios.

LITERATURE SURVEY

1) Deep Neural Network for Human Face Recognition

AUTHORS: [Priya Gupta](#) , [Nidhi Saxena](#)

Face recognition (FR), the process of identifying people through facial images, has numerous practical applications in the area of biometrics, information security, access control, law enforcement, smart cards and surveillance system. Convolutional Neural Networks (CovNets), a type of deep networks has been proved to be successful for FR. For real-time systems, some preprocessing steps like sampling needs to be done before using to CovNets. But then also complete images (all the pixel values) are passed as input to CovNets and all the steps (feature selection, feature extraction, training) are performed by the network. This is the reason that implementing CovNets are sometimes complex and time consuming. CovNets are at the nascent stage and the accuracies obtained are very high, so they have a long way to go. The paper proposes a new way of using a deep neural network (another type of deep

network) for face recognition. In this approach, instead of providing raw pixel values as input, only the extracted facial features are provided. This lowers the complexity of while providing the accuracy of 97.05% on Yale faces dataset.

2) Behaviour Based Data Dispatcher

AUTHORS: [Mohan Sai Singamsetti](#), [Mona Teja Kurakula](#)

Human life is a complex social structure. It is not possible for the humans to navigate without reading the other persons. They do it by identifying the faces. The state of response can be decided based on the mood of the opposite person. Whereas a person's mood can be figured out by observing his emotion (Facial Gesture). The aim of the project is to construct a "Facial emotion Recognition" model using DCNN (Deep convolutional neural network) in real time. The model is constructed using DCNN as it is proven that DCNN work with greater accuracy than CNN (convolutional neural network). The facial expression of humans is very dynamic in nature it changes in split seconds whether it may be Happy, Sad, Angry, Fear, Surprise, Disgust and Neutral etc. This project is to predict the emotion of the person in real time. Our brains have neural networks which are responsible for all kinds of thinking (decision making, understanding). This model tries to develop these decisions making and classification skills by training the machine. It can classify and predict the multiple faces and different emotions at the very same time. In order to obtain higher accuracy, we take the models which are trained over thousands of datasets.

3) Driver Fatigue Detection Based on Eye Tracking

AUTHORS : Mandalapu Sarada Devi

The International statistics shows that a large number of road accidents are caused by driver fatigue. Therefore, a system that can detect oncoming driver fatigue and issue timely warning could help in preventing many accidents, and consequently save money and reduce personal suffering. The authors have made an attempt to design a system that uses video camera that points directly towards the driver's face in order to detect fatigue. If the fatigue is detected a warning signal is issued to alert the driver. The authors have worked on the video files recorded by the camera. Video file is converted into frames. Once the eyes are located from each frame, by measuring the distances between the intensity changes in the eye area one can determine whether the eyes are open or closed. If the eyes are found closed for 5 consecutive frames, the system draws the conclusion that the driver is falling asleep and issues a warning signal. The algorithm is proposed, implemented, tested, and found working satisfactorily.

4) Driver Drowsiness Detection System Based on Feature Representation Learning Using Various Deep Networks

AUTHORS : Sanghyuk Park, Fei Pan, Sunghun Kang, Chang D. Yoo

Statistics have shown that 20% of all road accidents are fatigue-related, and drowsy

detection is a car safety algorithm that can alert a snoozing driver in hopes of preventing an accident. This paper proposes a deep architecture referred to as deep drowsiness detection (DDD) network for learning effective features and detecting drowsiness given a RGB input video of a driver. The DDD network consists of three deep networks for attaining global robustness to background and environmental variations and learning local facial movements and head gestures important for reliable detection. The outputs of the three networks are integrated and fed to a softmax classifier for drowsiness detection. Experimental results show that DDD achieves 73.06% detection accuracy on NTHU-drowsy driver detection benchmark dataset.

SYSTEM ANALYSIS:

EXISTING SYSTEM:

driving supporter schemes decreased the danger of four-wheeler accidents, and investigations depicted weariness to be a major reason of four wheeler accidents. A car organization announced an idea that whole deadly accidents (17%) would be attributed to weary drivers. Many revisions showed by Volkswagen AG specify that 5-25% of all accidents are produced by the sleeping of driver. The lack of concentration damage steering actions and decrease response period, and

revisions illustrated that sleepiness raises threat of crashes demand for a dependable intelligent driver sleepiness sensing system. The aim is to create an intelligent processing scheme to avoid road accidents. This can be done by period of time monitoring the drowsiness and warning driver of inattention to prevent accidents.

DISADVANTAGES OF EXISTING SYSTEM:

- It is not suitable for real-time processing.
- The existing system uses the orientation of facial characteristics for drowsy detection.
- based on three factors such as physiological, behavioral, and vehicle-based measurements. But these approaches pose some disadvantages in certain real time scenarios.

Algorithm: Learning Vector Quantization (LVQ), Support Vector Machines (SVM)

PROPOSED SYSTEM:

Our proposed system will provide a solution for monitoring driver's drowsiness. The cons of the existing system in extracting only selected hand-crafted features is overcome by using custom-designed CNN by giving an input driver image. Now the driver will be continuously monitored by a webcam. The video captured is converted into a sequence of frames. For each frame, the face and eye are detected using predefined classifiers available in opencv called haar cascade classifiers. Eye images are extracted and sent to a series of 2D CNN layers (5x5, 3x3 kernel valid padding), max-pooling layers(2x2) and finally, the fully connected dense layer classifies whether eyes are closed or not. A score is calculated based on eye closure. If both eyes are closed consecutively in 15 frames then the system predicts as

drowsy and an alarm sound is triggered to alert the car operator. The categorization of driver drowsiness is done correctly and the normalization issues in the existing model are eliminated by using customdesigned CNN.

ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM:

- If the eyes are both closed, we increase the score and when eyes are open, we decrease the score. We are drafting the outcome to display the actual time condition of the driver.
- approach enables us to identify driver's face characteristics like eye closure percentage, eye-mouth aspect ratios, blink rate, yawning, head movement.

Algorithm: Convolutional Neural Network; Data Augmentation Deep Learning.

CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK

Convolutional Neural Network is one of the main categories to do image classification and image recognition in neural networks. Scene labeling, objects detections, and face recognition, etc., are some of the areas where convolutional neural networks are widely used.

CNN takes an image as input, which is classified and process under a certain category such as dog, cat, lion, tiger, etc. The computer sees an image as an array of pixels and depends on the resolution of the image. Based on image resolution, it will see as $h * w * d$, where h = height w = width and d = dimension. For example, An RGB image is $6 * 6 * 3$ array of the matrix, and the grayscale image is $4 * 4 * 1$ array of the matrix.

In CNN, each input image will pass through a sequence of convolution layers along with pooling, fully connected layers, filters (Also known as kernels). After that, we will apply the Soft-max function to classify an object with probabilistic values 0 and 1.

CONCLUSION

A model for drowsiness sensing depends on effective CNN architecture, planned to observe drowsiness based on eye closure. The implementation started preparing image datasets for both open and closed eyes. 75% of the data set is used for the custom-designed CNN training and the balance 25% of the dataset is utilized for test purposes. First, the information video is transformed into frames and in each frame, the face and eyes are detected. The enhanced CNN supplied an automated and effective learned characteristics that aid us to categorize the opening or closing of eyes. If the closing of eyes occur in 15 successive frames, an alarm is triggered to alert

the driver. The proposed CNN gives a training accuracy of 97% and a testing accuracy of 67%. For future works, extra face characteristics can be added to give more accuracy in detection. We can also combine vehicle driving pattern information obtained using On-Board Diagnostics sensors with the facial features extracted.

FURTHER ENHANCEMENT:

The proposed CNN gives a training accuracy of 97% and a testing accuracy of 67%. For future works, extra face characteristics can be added to give more accuracy in detection. We can also combine vehicle driving pattern information obtained using On-Board Diagnostics sensors with the facial features extracted.

REFERENCES

- [1] Computationally efficient face detection; b. Scholkopf-a. Blake, s. Romdhani, and p. Torr.
- [2] Use of the hough transformation to detect lines and curves in picture; r. Duda and p. E. Hart.

- [3] Jain, face detection in color images; r. L. Hsu, m. Abdelmottaleb, and a. K. Jain.
- [4] Open/closed eye analysis for drowsiness detection; p.r. Tabrizi and r. A. Zoroofi.
- [5] Kai Shu, Suhang Wang, Huan Liu, Understanding User Profiles on Social Media for Fake News Detection, 2018, MIPR.
- [6] M. Suganya and H. Anandakumar, Handover based spectrum allocation in cognitive radio networks, 2013 International Conference on Green Computing, Communication and Conservation of Energy (ICGCE), Dec. 2013. doi:10.1109/icgce.2013.6823431. doi:10.4018/978-1-5225-5246-8.ch012
- [7] Haldorai and A. Ramu, An Intelligent-Based Wavelet Classifier for Accurate Prediction of Breast Cancer, Intelligent Multidimensional Data and Image Processing, pp. 306–319.
- [8] Amitabha Dey, RafsanZani Rafi, ShahriarParash, Fake News Pattern Recognition using Linguistic Analysis, 2018, ICIEV and ICIVPR
- [9] Karne, R. K. ., & Sreeja, T. K. . (2023). PMLC- Predictions of Mobility and Transmission in a Lane-Based Cluster VANET Validated on Machine Learning. International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication, 11(5s), 477–483. <https://doi.org/10.17762/ijritcc.v11i5s.7109>
- [10] Radha Krishna Karne and Dr. T. K. Sreeja (2022), A Novel Approach for Dynamic Stable Clustering in VANET Using Deep Learning (LSTM) Model. IJEER 10(4), 1092-1098. DOI: 10.37391/IJEER.100454.
- [11] Reddy, Kallem Niranjana, and Pappu Venkata Yasoda Jayasree. "Low Power Strain and Dimension Aware SRAM Cell Design Using a New Tunnel FET and Domino Independent Logic." International Journal of Intelligent Engineering & Systems 11, no. 4 (2018).
- [12] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Design of a Dual Doping Less Double Gate Tfet and Its Material Optimization Analysis on a 6t Sram Cells."
- [13] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Low power process, voltage, and temperature (PVT) variations aware improved tunnel FET on 6T SRAM cells." Sustainable Computing: Informatics and Systems 21 (2019): 143-153.
- [14] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Survey on improvement of PVT aware variations in tunnel FET on SRAM cells." In 2017 International Conference on Current Trends in Computer, Electrical, Electronics and Communication (CTCEEC), pp. 703-705. IEEE, 2017